

A LINGUISTIC STUDY OF FRENCH ACQUISITIONS

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Abstract:

In this article, a linguistic study of French acquisitions will be analyzed. As it is known vocabulary of each language consists of borrowed words, which are regularly updated and enriched. This, of course, is closely related to the process of the emergence of science, technology, and innovative innovations. Also, the acquisition of words from one language to another is a natural process, sometimes they are assimilated directly and sometimes through indirect expression.

Key words: French Acquisitions, linguistic approaches, indirect expression, accepted words, semantic and stylistic differentiation.

Introduction. At this point, we considered it permissible to quote the following opinion expressed by L.L. Nelyubin about possessive words, that is, "to express new concepts, to express existing concepts in a more differentiated way, and to define previously unknown items, it is a reference to the lexical fund of other languages . " ¹U. Weinreich expresses the opinion that borrowed words are the process of filling dictionaries with new objects, persons, places, and concepts ², while L.P. Krysin expresses scientific comments that it is a natural development process of languages, which is evaluated as "the tendency of semantic and stylistic differentiation of means of expression" ³.

Agreeing with the opinion of the above scholars, it can be said that the appearance of borrowed words in another language reflects the development process of any language. Similar processes are observed in the history of the Uzbek language. As part of the research, we are focusing on the history, reasons and ways of the introduction of French loanwords into the Uzbek language . *Extralinguistic reasons:*

- 1) Inter-national and inter-state closeness and cooperation of peoples;
- 2) The appearance of a certain new concept and subject in each language;
- 3) Innovations in various fields of human activity;
- 4) Political, economic and social conditions of the emergence of internationalisms in the language.

The most important intralinguistic reason:

- 1) Non-availability of an alternative lexical unit in the receiving language (*advance, adventurer, aviation, ballad, banker...*) ;

¹ Nelyubin L.L. Tolkov st perevodovedchesky dictionary. M., 2006. -S.78.

² Weinreich U. Language contacts: Status and problem analysis. Kiev ., 1979. -S. 263

³ Chrysin L.P. _ Yazykovoe zaimstvovanie kak problema diachronicheskoy sotsiolingvistiki M., 1993. - S.131-151.

2) The possibility of using a newly acquired word instead of a descriptive phrase existing in the receiving language (*les accessoires-decorations, le bouquiniste - bookseller, le credit- debt*);

3) The tendency to supplement the expressive means of the language with the help of borrowed words (*boutique, vernissage, croissant*) to increase the stylistic coloring of the language.

The history of the origin of the adopted words goes back to various historical events and phenomena. It is known that Uzbekistan was a part of the former USSR countries and a lot of words in the Uzbek language were introduced through the Russian language. And Russia has had very good cooperation with France for many centuries. One of the reasons for this is that in the 11th century, the daughter of Yaroslav the Wise, Anna became the queen of France, that is, she married King Henry I.

Literal Review. It was during this period that many French words entered the Russian language. By the 16th-18th centuries, it can be seen in the dictionaries of this direction that the French words were well established in the Russian vocabulary. It has been shown in a number of studies that the acquisition of English and French into the Russian language penetrated into various fields. Olga Velichko, while researching English-French adaptations of medical terms in the Russian language, shows that in Russia in the 18th-19th centuries, biology, zoology, physics, chemistry, and especially in the field of medicine flourished in the natural fields⁴. It is known that in the 17th and 19th centuries, especially in the world-wide discoveries of French scientists, the services of famous microbiologists such as Louis Pasteur and Emile Roux are incomparable. The publication of articles on the treatment of diphtheria and toxicology by Emil Roux was the impetus for this. Due to the famous French writer and philosopher Jacques Jacques Rousseau's research on reforming his education based on the development of human emotions, French influences have also entered the field of psychology. The scientist classifies the process of assimilation of French words into the Russian language as follows:

1) Simple assimilation by adding suffixes, for example: *tubaj, drainage, tamponage, patronage, drainage* (65%).

2) The hybrid terms are a mixture of English and French acquisitions, i.e. *depo - antigene - depo antigen, oil -adjuvant vaccine - vaksina s maslyanym adyuvantom* (2.7%).

3) Motivated phraseological appropriations are very small, for example, *déjà vecu* has already seen everything, *déjà vu* has already been seen (1.4%).

4) Calculating acquisitions, for example, *antibodies -anticorps*.

5) Eponyms are, for example, frame syndrome, which French doctor Lucie Frey called *Mantoux's probe, which means vaccination, reaction*. Such acquisitions make up 20.4%.

6) Appropriations of authorship terms from microorganisms or the names of the first founders. For example, the word "*bacterium*" was introduced to science in 1851 by the French biologist and physician Casimir Dzhhofer Daven. The term "*Potology*" was used by XV in the century living creativity a French doctor who did and scientist Fernell by note done. Such In his classification, the scientist shows that borrowings made up 7.3% of the Russian language⁵.

⁴ Velichko .V. Anglo -French loanwords and Russian medical terminology. Autoref .d iss ... kand.filol.nauk . Atrakhan , 2010.

⁵ Velichko O.V. Anglo -French loanwords and Russian medical terminology. Autoref .d iss ... kand.filol.nauk . Atrakhan , 2010. -S. 14.

of foreign scientists V.M.Aristova ⁶, L.P.Krysin ⁷, R.P.Samusev, N.I.Goncharov, scientists mention that acquisitions appear in the second language through phonetic, lexical, semantic changes.⁸

Research and Methodology. It should be noted that scholars have different approaches to the process of acquiring words and their transfer from one language to another. Some scientists advocate the appearance of terms in dictionaries of other languages and say that it gives the language attractiveness and individuality ⁹, while other scientists express the opinion that it leads to corruption and contamination of the language ¹⁰. In our opinion, the acquisition of terms from one language to another is characterized by the absence of an alternative of this term or a lexeme with the same meaning in the receiving language. Half of the 240,000 words included in the Oxford English Dictionary, one of the world's largest dictionaries, are medical terms. In our opinion, it is justified that the terms belonging to a certain field enter the reserve of another language because there is no alternative in another language. In this regard, V.G. Kostomarov believes that the sound of the new ¹¹term in the press, radio and television shows that the rapid development of mass communication has its effect on all speech styles. . Agreeing with the opinion of A.A. Bragin, word and language creativity is determined by certain conditions. Language reflects changes in society, ideas, culture, scientific development and daily news ¹². M.A. Breiter believes that the lexical level of the language is more mobile and variable than the phonetic and grammatical levels, so it acts as a barometer of social changes and the wishes of the members of the language community ¹³.

Khurshida Safarova, in her scientific article, analyzes the French loanwords that have entered the English language, the history of their entry into the English language, the reasons and ways of assimilation.

- Normandy invasion period ;
- The period of domestication ;
- XVII-XVIII centuries ¹⁴.

Analysis and Results. Also, in this work, "as a result of the enthusiasm of the English aristocracy and bourgeoisie for French customs, traditions and tastes, many French lexemes entered the English language. A number of such words entered the vocabulary of the English language as slang, for example, *chant - to beg, to beg; gent - money*, etc. Borrowings from the French language continue to fill the vocabulary of the English language in the following

⁶Aristova V.M. Anglo-Russian language contacts (anglitsizmy v russkom yazyke) -L ., 1978.

⁷Krysin L.P. Zametki o inoyazychnyx slovak// Russkaya rech. - M., 2000. No. 6. - S. 38-40.

⁸Samusev R.P., Goncharov N.I. Eponymy and morphology. - M. 1989. -S. 352.

⁹ Shansky M.M., Babrova T.A. Lexicology of the modern Russian language. -M., 1972. -S.253.

¹⁰ Protchenko I.F. Lexicon and slovobrazovanie russkogo yazyka sovetskoy epoxi. Sotsiolinguistichesky aspekt./: Otv. ed. G.V. Stepanov. 2 - izd. dope -M .: Nauka, 1985. -351p.

¹¹ Kostomarov V.G. Yazykovoy vkus epoxy. -M., 1994. -S.274.

¹² Bragina A.A. Istoria slov v jizni narod a. - M., 1989 .

¹³ Brighter M.A. The process of linguistic borrowing as a method of realization of communicative needs in the frame of mejkulturnogo interaction // Lingvokognitivnye problemy mejkulturnoy kommunikatsii. M.: Philology, 1997. - S. 49-65.

¹⁴ Safarova Kh. A diachronic and synchronic analysis of acquisitions from English into French. News of UzMU. 2022. 1/1/2/ -B .273-276.

centuries" ¹⁵and emphasizes the continuation of the process of borrowings into other languages.

Yu.V.Kobenko and T.I.Meremkulova published a dictionary of French loanwords adapted to the German language. This dictionary includes 3,813 French words and their etymology and information, mainly words that entered the German literary language in the 11th and 20th centuries are arranged in 24 alphabets ¹⁶. Also, in the preface of this book, the scientist expresses his thoughts about the process of the introduction of the French words that entered the German language as a result of political, economic and cultural influences. He emphasizes that the vocabulary of any language is not free of borrowed words, neologisms and introductions.

Scientists A.N. Antseva and E.A. While studying the process of the introduction of French borrowings into the English language and its impact on the language, the Abuevas clarify this issue by analyzing historical processes. In 1066, under the influence of the Norman invasion, the process of the Normans entering England, Norman speakers occupying a place in the English administration, as a result of the assimilation of the Anglo-Norman language, caused the old French language to become the language of state and cultural administration. English is spoken in the villages, but the majority of the urban population speaks French, even the names of animals and foods have been spoken in both French and English for many years. For example, such as *cow, sheep, ox, viande, rôti, de porc*. *Action* in French (*accioun* in French), *beauty* (*beate* in French), *carpenter* (*carpentier* in French); *duke* - *duke* (*duc* in old French). In particular, rapid assimilation of French institutions was observed in the state, military, and religious spheres. Including *minister (en) – ministre (fr)*; *honor (en) – honor (fr)*; *army (en) – army*; *noble – noble (fr)*; *abbey (en) – abbey (fr)*.¹⁷

P. Nishanov, while studying the diplomatic lexicon that entered the Uzbek language from the French language, clarified the process of their introduction, formation and development into the Uzbek language and made the following analysis:

"Let's look at some of the terms that entered the Uzbek language from the French language through the Russian language: *attache* - "a small diplomatic color; a diplomatic officer representing a particular field". In French, the word *attaché* means "attached". At the present time, there are combinations with the word *attache*: military *attache*, military - naval *attache*, military - air force *attache*, special *attache* (agriculture, industry, culture, technology, finance, trade, science), press *attache*, honorary *attache*" ¹⁸. Also, the scientist positively evaluates the introduction and use of words in languages that are not related to each other, which serves the enrichment of each language.

In his treatise, N.E.Umarkho'jaev briefly dwells on the words adopted from French to German and divides them into three periods. These are:

¹⁵Safarova Kh. A diachronic and synchronic analysis of acquisitions from English into French. News of UzMU. 2022. 1/1/2/ –B.276.

¹⁶ Kobenko Yu Yu.V., Merimkulova T.I. Dictionary of French loanwords and modern German language. - Tomsk, 2020.

¹⁷ Umarho'jaev M. German language. Lexicology, Lexicography. Phraseology, Phraseography. - Andijan, 2010.

¹⁸Nishonov P.P. Formation of lexicon of the diplomatic field in French and Uzbek languages. <https://journal.fledu.uz/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2022/02/francuz-va-ozbek-tillarida-diplomatik-soha-lexikasining-shakllanishiye.pdf>

" **The first period** includes the 12th-14th centuries. During this period, a number of words related to French court life and chivalry were adopted. M.: Turnier, Lanze, Visier, Banner; Due to the strong influence of the French language on the lives of European peoples, not only French words, but also some word-forming tools were adopted.

– **The second period** - the XVI-XVII centuries, that is, the flourishing period of French absolutism - the period of King Louis XIV. During this period, the French language had a strong influence not only on the German language, but also on many other languages, especially the courtiers and high-ranking people used to speak German with French words added. For example, *Monsieur, Madame, Mademoiselle*.

– **The third period** includes the 18th-19th centuries and is connected with the events of the French bourgeois revolution of 1789. Many political terms expressing the spirit of the time entered the German vocabulary. For example, Anarchist, Brokratie, Emigrant, Jakobiner, Koalition, Komitee, Konstitution, Monarchist, Propaganda, Reaktion, Abgeordneter, Wahlmann, abstimmen, einstimmig, Stimmenmehrheit, Nationalversammlung, Fraktion, Veto¹⁹.

The French language had a strong influence not only on the German language, but also on other European languages at that time. We can clearly see this if we look at the history of the Russian language and literature. Later, through the Russian language, French words entered the Uzbek language from the languages of other nations of the former union. For example, a restaurant, pardon, wardrobe, etc.

Words related to fashion are borrowed from the French language - Mode, Matresse, Cavallier, gallant, Pldsier, Compliment, Reputation, Ptspel (Volkmenge), Ball, Ballet, Masquerade, amsieren, Promenade. A number of words related to construction, equipment, and gardening were borrowed from the French language during these centuries. M.: Balcony, Terasse, Bassin, Grotte, Galerie, Loge, Niscue; words related to clothes and make-up: Kostm, Corsette, Percke, Pomade, Friseur, Parfm; Words related to food and drinks - Serviette, Rogaut, Omlette, Sauce, marinieren, Kompott, Konfiture, Marmalade, Torte, Bisquitt, Limonade, servieren, Frikasse²⁰.

Zebo Kadirova, while researching the structural semantic aspects of words acquired in the German language, divides them into the following groups:

1. Adopted words whose pronunciation directly corresponds;
2. Mispronounced borrowed words;
3. Words with multiple meanings;
4. Words with broad meanings.

scholar considers words that have different meanings depending on the context to be broad-meaning borrowed words. This study differs from other studies in that it divided the acquired words into groups such as polysemous and broad-sense.

Conclusion. Navbahor Kuldoshova researches the national cultural characteristics of sports terminology in French and Uzbek languages, and while doing a comparative analysis of the words learned in this field, she emphasizes the acquisition of words and phrases learned from one language to another and the expansion of the vocabulary of the language with them. Also,

¹⁹ Umarho'jaev M. German language. Lexicology, Lexicography. Phraseology, Phraseography. - Andijan, 2010. - P.24-25.

²⁰ Umarho'jaev M. German language. Lexicology, Lexicography. Phraseology, Phraseography. - Andijan, 2010. - P.24-25.

N. Koldoshova shows that in the process of acquiring words, special attention should be paid to the following methods, namely:

- 1) by acquiring words from other languages;
- 2) loss of some words used in the language;
- 3) it is necessary to pay attention to methods such as changing the meaning of words (complete change of word meaning, appearance of homonyms, expansion and narrowing of word meanings) ²¹.

So, in this paragraph, we have considered the process, period, methods of assimilation of Rantsuz assimilation into other languages as examples of the works of foreign and Uzbek scientists. The following general situations were observed in the works of all scientists:

- Dividing the assimilation process into periods;
- The relevance of the process of appropriation to political, historical and social reasons;
- appropriation of terms related to a certain field due to the absence of an alternative;
- words acquired as a result of political, economic, scientific and cultural relations between peoples;
- the process of word acquisition due to the bilingual phenomenon;
- innovations in various fields of human activity;
- assimilation of words through eponyms.

The opinions of scientists about acquisitions can be divided into two groups, namely:

- the appearance of borrowed words in other language dictionaries gives the language attractiveness and individuality;
- causes the language to be corrupted and polluted.

Analyzing the opinions of all scientists in our research, we support the fact that borrowed words serve to enrich the language and the tendency to increase the stylistic color in the language and fill the expressive means of the language.

²¹ Koldoshova N. National cultural characteristics of sports terminology in French and Uzbek languages. Autoref. Diss... phil.science.doc. -Bukhara, 2020. -B.21.

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